

FINAL REPORT

Baseline information and awareness raising. Cambalhão seagrass meadow, Sado estuary, Portugal. May – October 2023.

INTRODUCTION

Cambalhão seagrass meadow is a novel seagrass in the Sado estuary, “seeded by the hand of nature”. The location of this meadow, within the calm waters of the 1km wide inner bay of the Cambalhão sandy island, is also known as the “Carabean of the Sado estuary”. Every summer, hundreds of boats anchor on this bay, close to the beach (and to the meadow) to spend the day. Facing the potential impact of the navigational and anchoring practices in degrading the “young” meadow, Ocean Alive triggered a search for funding, aiming at creating baseline information, promoting awareness of the importance of the meadow and creating guardians among the users of the island that would safeguard the meadow.

Figure 1. Aerial view of the Cambalhão Island, on the left, and of the Tróia peninsula on the right. ©Protect Blue.

Sustainable Surf partnered with Ocean Alive to provide funding for delivering (1) the first baseline research on the Cambalhão seagrass meadow – area estimation,

mapping, species composition and biodiversity; (2) education and community awareness targeting mainly local maritime tourist enterprises (MTs) as ambassadors (“Seagrass Guardians”) to enable the protection of the meadow by good navigational and anchoring practices. The 5 month project started in May 2023. The partnership also provided the capacitation of Ocean Alive team in mapping, by supporting the training and the acquisition of a drone and assessor equipment. As a complement, subsequent systematic monitoring of the meadow over 2 years, to provide evidence of the impact of the project.

This report provides information on the services and deliveries according to the “statement of the work” – Exhibit 1 – of the Services Agreement between Ocean Alive and Sustainable Surf.

The report is divided into three parts. The first section describes the methodology used in the scientific and awareness and education approaches. In the following section we present the results and discuss and comment on our findings. The last part of this report aims at triggering next steps by introducing complementary and new approaches to the present work.

WRAP UP – the project in numbers

Before the project started only anecdotal information existed about the Cambalhão seagrass meadow and the knowledge of this meadow was restricted to a few users of the area. Nowadays, baseline information about the meadow is being spread, hundreds of users of the Cambalhão island are aware of the meadow and of the good navigational and anchoring practices, and local MTs are willing to collaborate in safeguarding and spread the word about the importance of the meadow.

In an attempt to summarize the most relevant numbers achieved by the project here we point out:

1 novel seagrass meadow age less than 5 years old at the Cambalhão inner bay, composed of 202 patches, globally enclosing an area of 0.35 hectares, composed of 2 species of marine plants – *Zostera marina* and *Zostera nolteii* – whose mean densities varied between 80 and 160 (SD: 89.08 ud/m²) shoots per square meter (ud/m²) and 592.00 ud/m², respectively.

On august weekend days, between 58 and 128 boats were counted anchored at the Cambalhão intertidal and subtidal bottom bay. 543 summer users (represented 185 boats) became aware of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow and of good navigational and anchoring practices.

19 staff members of 8 maritime tourist enterprises with a direct relation with the Cambalhão island received training and support materials about the Cambalhão seagrass meadow.

Figure 2. Underwater pictures of the seagrass species *Zostera marina* taking by Protect Blue on the visit to the project area on the 28th of August. ©Protect Blue

METHODOLOGY

BASELINE INFORMATION OF THE CAMBALHÃO SEAGRASS MEADOW

1. Mapping and area estimation

The mapping and area estimation of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow presented in this report was calculated from aerial images of the meadow, taken by a drone. In order to prepare the georeferenced coordinates of the flight, the Ocean Alive team conducted several preliminary exploratory activities.

The exploratory activities aimed at gaining a preliminary understanding of the location, distribution and dimensions of the meadow's patches and which species of marine plants compose the meadows. These exploratory activities were carried out by members of the Ocean Alive team and consisted in boat surveys, shoreline walks, and exploratory drone and diving apneas to gather relevant data, before and during the startime of the project: August 24th, September 11th and November 26th of 2022 and on the January 31st, March 13th, April 14th, July 28th supported by 2 team members of Protect Blue, and august 5th of 2023.

To characterize and record the location of subtidal seagrass patches 3 boat surveys were conducted in the Cambalhão inner bay at a speed slow enough that allowed us to visualize patches from the surface. When a seagrass patch was located, the georeferenced coordinates were recorded with a Garmin 64S hand GPS and the seagrass species identified. In instances where surface visibility was insufficient for direct species identification, apnea surveys were conducted to gather information about the species composition of the patches. Boat support was provided by the Sado Estuary Natural Reserve (RNES) and by local maritime touristic enterprise (MT) "Boat Center" and "Rotas do Sal".

To characterize and record the location of intertidal seagrass patches, snorkeling and shoreline walks were performed at low tide. The location of the seagrass patches was also recorded using a Garmin 64S hand GPS. Data on the plant species composition and of any other observation considered relevant, such as the presence of algae or the impacts of human activities on the area, were also recorded. On the 26th of November 2022, Ocean Alive had the opportunity to gather exploratory drone images of the distributions of the patches, a courtesy of the Portuguese enterprise ©Playsolutions audio visuals. Together with the data collected during exploratory activities, this allowed us to estimate the boundaries, and to assess the species composition of the seagrass meadow. This information was essential for planning subsequent drone flights.

In order to prepare the flight routes and subsequent drone image compilation and analysis, the Ocean Alive team assisted to a 3h workshop on the 14th of June given by Dr. Niels Svane form South Denmark University. The drone flights to map and estimate the area of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow were conducted on the 10th of August 2023. The drone operator was hired by Ocean Alive, after verification of

the technical and logistic facilities appropriated for that task. This option was chosen in order to guarantee that the mapping could be finished within the time frame of the project. Our team was responsible for planning the flight route and for orientation in the field during the flights. We include the authorization documents required (Annex I). Overall, weather conditions on that day were suitable for conducting the drone flight, with low intensity winds ranging from 3-8 knots and enough water clarity to be able to distinguish the seagrass patches located at the maximum depth (~5m) from the surface.

Two drone flights were conducted using a UAV platform model DJI® Air 2S. The first flight was performed at an altitude of 100m and the second one, at 3-20m. The trajectory of the flights was planned and executed using the autonomous flight app “Litchi” (VC Technology Ltd © 2023) (Figure 3). Image front and side overlaps were set to a range of 70-75% and flight speed to 3.5 m/s, according to Thomasberger *et al.*, 2023. The images were taken with a nadir viewing angle (~90°).

Figure 3. Picture showing the flight plan on the app “Litchi” (VC Technology Ltd © 2023) over a low altitude image of a seagrass patch (Image above). Ocean Alive team (image below, on the left) visualizing the resultant photographs taken (below right) ©Ocean Alive

During the flight conducted at 100m of altitude, 78 photographs were taken covering the whole project area, while during the flight at low altitude (3-5m), 24 photographs were taken at specific points (n=9) previously identified in the field as calibration points (CP). The selection of these CP was done based on previous information gathered during exploratory activities, namely the presence/absence of features of interest (Algae; *Zostera marina*; *Zostera noltii*; bare sediment, or a mix of those) so that afterwards, those low altitude images could be used to confirm the presence of seagrass and therefore, account for area and mapping. As an example, in Figure 4 we illustrate the procedure of a calibration point at different altitudes (A-100m, B-20m and C-12m), where the presence of *Zostera noltii* was previously identified.

Figure 4. Aerial photographs taken by drone at 100m, 20m and 12m of altitude, on the 10th of August from a previously characterized point with the presence of the seagrass species *Z. noltii*. ©Ocean Alive.

As a result, one georeferenced orthomosaic was created for the 100m of altitude flight by stitching the obtained images using the image processing software Agisoft Metashape Professional® ver. 2.0.2 (Agisoft, 2023). Finally, in order to estimate the area of the Cambalhão meadow, the orthomosaic was uploaded to QGIS® software (2023) and polygons were created manually on seagrass patches based on visual inspection and comparison with the CP. The area of the meadow (ha) was calculated automatically as the sum of the area of each polygon.

2. Baseline conditions

2.1 Biological characterization of the meadow

Besides the exploratory observations described in the previous section, the biological characterization of the meadow was conducted in June 2023 aiming at (1) collecting baseline data on biological indicators of the plants composing the meadow and (2) opportunistically recording and identifying the species of fauna and flora observed in the seagrass patches.

The biological indicators collected were shoot density and canopy height. Data on these indicators was collected along 6 transect line dives on the middle subtidal section of the meadow, by 2 marine biologist of Ocean Alive team. These dives were conducted on the 12th and 13th of June, with the operational boat support of the Sado Estuary Natural Reserve.

The starting point for each transect line was chosen based on the estimated location of seagrass patches identified in previous exploratory surveys together with visual identification of the patches from the boat when possible, at an approximated depth of 3.5m. Each point was separated by ~ 100-170m in order to cover fractions of the whole project area (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Representation on the map of the location and coordinates of the starting points of the 6 baseline dives conducted on the 12th and 13th of June. ©Google Satellite.

The coordinates of the starting point of each line transect dive were marked by a hand GPS Garmin 64S from the boat and was signaled by a surface buoy attached

by a line to weights positioned on the bottom. Each transect line was 25m long following a perpendicular direction to the coast. In order to collect the data, the divers followed the transect line and recorded a video along the overall 25m of length using an Olympus TG Tough standing at the center of the line and at the same depth, when conditions allowed so (Figure 6).

Data on the biological indicators - density (ud/m²) and canopy height (cm) - was recorded in every seagrass patch observed. The sampling method followed Borum *et al.*, 2004 (*European seagrasses: an introduction to monitoring and management*). Seagrass density was measured by counting the number of individual shoots present within a sampling quadrat of 15x15cm located randomly within the patch that was being sampled (Figure 7). Results were afterwards extrapolated to m². Canopy height was sampled by measuring the longest leaf of 5 shoots chosen randomly at each patch. Visual census and photographs were taken of the fauna and flora encountered along the transects.

Figure 6. Picture of a marine biologist from Ocean Alive team conducting a video line transect.
©Ocean Alive

In order to estimate the age of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow, and to gain a better understanding of the meadow's development and its dynamic over the past years, we combined satellite images from years 2014, 2018, 2020 and 2023 (Figure 8) ,with the perspective of 8 local individuals who frequently visit the area and are

familiar with it, for work reasons (maritime tourist enterprises staff members) or for leisure (spear gun fishing and weekend and summer holiday days) We administered questionnaires to them, asking about old the seagrass meadow and Cambalhão Island are, whether the meadow has been expanding or not and what are the main natural and anthropogenic factors affecting the Cambalhão seagrass meadow (Annex II). The questionnaires were conducted through a phone call in October 2023.

Figure 7. Pictures of a marine biologist from Ocean Alive measuring seagrass density (above) and canopy height (below). ©Ocean Alive

Figure 8. Satellite images from years 2014, 2018, 2020 and 2023 ©Google Earth.

2.2 Threats and pressures

Based on data gathered from baseline condition surveys and dives, monitoring dives, and interviews conducted with 8 local individuals who frequent the project area, we have collected valuable insights into the natural and anthropogenic factors that appear to be adversely impacting the prosperity of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow.

Figure 9. Boat anchoring on the top intertidal patches of seagrass. ©Ocean Alive

EDUCATION AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

1. Ambassadors among local maritime tourism companies – “Seagrass Guardians”.

In order to improve the role of local maritime tourism (MTs) enterprises as “Seagrass Guardians” in safeguarding the Cambalhão seagrass meadow, Ocean Alive’s team approached all the MTs working in the Sado Estuary that have a direct relation with Cambalhão island. The targeted companies develop activities such as dolphin watching, boat transfers and private onboard events. All provide boat transfers to the island. Our main goal was to share relevant information that they could learn from and use when interacting with tourists they would encounter during the summer months in the Sado Estuary, which represents the high season for maritime tourism work. By educating these local maritime tourism workers, the task of changing behaviors and raising awareness towards the importance of seagrass meadows would be multiplied by an increasing number of people other than Ocean Alive’s team. The approach of Ocean Alive was based on (1) one to one sessions of education and awareness targeting MTs staff, (2) engagement of the MTs in logistic support of the Ocean Alive awareness campaign towards the users of the Cambalhão island and (3) one to one sessions of education and awareness targeting users of Cambalhão island and meadow, during all weekend days of august 2023 (see following section).

(1) Educational and awareness sessions - MTs. In March 2023, Ocean Alive conducted an educational event about the importance of seagrass meadows targeting local MTs. This event had the partnership of Setúbal Bay association, whose associates are local MTs. Relevant information was shared with the workers of maritime tourism companies such as what are seagrass and how are they different from algae? Why are seagrass meadows important to the balance of our daily lives? Where are they located in the Sado Estuary? Why is Cambalhão seagrass meadow important and how can MTs have a role in its protection? What are the main causes for seagrass degradation and what can we do about them? Additionally, the results from Ocean Alive’s previous year of community and restoration work were shared, along with supporting underwater footage. This learning experience was complemented with a snorkeling activity in the Ponta do Adoxe seagrass meadow, one of the most emblematic and of easy access meadows of the Sado Estuary, where participants got to experience firsthand the sensation of swimming in a seagrass meadow. During July and August, Ocean Alive’s team initiated one to one educational and awareness sessions targeting only the MTs that have a direct with the Cambalhão island and meadow. To support this specific approach, Ocean Alive developed an information kit with contents on the Cambalhão seagrass meadow - satellite images of how the Cambalhão sand bank has developed throughout the years, the location and above vision of the meadow from drone footage, underwater footage about the underlying Cambalhão seagrass meadow, examples of inhabiting fauna and flora and

demonstration of scuba diving monitoring by our team – an information of good navigational practices. In addition, posters and leaflets were also provided about the location of the meadows in the estuary and eco-conscious boating practices. As a complement, [a QR Code](#) was also shared where different footage and maps about the Cambalhão seagrass meadow is available.

(2) Engagement of the MTs to secure transportation of Ocean Alive´s team to and from Cambalhão island. By partnering with local maritime tourism companies, Ocean Alive found a way to give them a role in contributing to direct awareness actions of the weekend summer users of the island and meadow.

After the month of august, these specific MTs were subjected to a questionnaire, in order to evaluate how the shared information impacted their daily working routine. (Annex II).

2. Awareness towards sustainable anchoring practices – Cambalhão boat summer users.

(3) For the past two years and during the summer months of July and August, Ocean Alive has implemented an awareness campaign directed at boat owners that choose seagrass meadow areas to spend their summer day. The campaign is located at beaches close to seagrass meadows, harbors and marinas (Figure 10).

In the summer of 2023, the campaign was financed by Activo Bank - Ocean Alive partner in a seagrass restoration project. For the first time, the Cambalhão sand bank was included as a target area. This was possible due to the collaboration established with the local marine tourism companies and boat users providing the transportation of Ocean Alive monitors and volunteers.

The main goal of the campaign is one-to-one awareness sessions with the users of the Cambalhão meadow. These sessions consist of conversations, engagement and dialogue with the local boat owners and their families or associated group. Through this method, we share valuable information on the importance of the seagrass meadows and promote eco-conscious behaviors that everyone can adopt to help conserve the seagrass meadows of the Sado estuary. An example of these behaviors is to be careful with the area where anchors are deployed, as when anchors are dropped in seagrass areas they can easily damage and uproot the marine plants and promote seagrass degradation (Cunha & Serrão, 2013). Another example is to be careful with how lowered the motors are in seagrass areas, as the whirlpools generated to make the boat move can also have negative effects on the health of the seagrass meadow (Dunton & Schonberg, 2002).

As a complement, leaflets with summarized information were given to the summer users. Furthermore, [a QR Code](#) was also shared where different footage and maps about the Cambalhão seagrass meadow is available.

Figure 10. An example of an awareness session occurring in the Cambalhão sandbank. An Ocean Alive monitor is starting a dialogue about the importance of seagrass meadows and eco-conscious boating practices with a targeted group of people that had come to spend their summer day close to the seagrass meadow. ©Ocean Alive

MONITORING

For the purpose of monitoring reporting, we implemented a novel methodology, distinct from that used for determining baseline conditions according to transect dive surveys conducted in June 2023.

These previous line transects were primarily concentrated on the subtidal area of the meadow, which is situated close to the coastline.

Once having determined the area and mapping of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow, the new monitoring methodology aimed at providing a systematic record of the evolution of the meadow. In order to do so, the area of the meadow was sampled according to the degree of potential damage from boat navigation and anchoring, addressing the focus of this project. As a result, three sampling sections were defined. “The intertidal section” and the “subtidal middle section” of the Cambalhão meadow are the sections of the meadow closer to the island, these are areas where anchoring is frequent, which correspond to high and middle level of pressure, respectively. The “subtidal section” of the meadow is the area where boat navigation practices are less likely to damage the meadow, corresponding to a low level of pressure. In Figure 11 we present these coordinates established for each of the 3 sections of the meadow and their location on the map.

Point ID	Longitude	Latitude
1	-8.92023781	38.47919371
2	-8.91978337	38.47892087
3	-8.92051978	38.48073085
4	-8.92024619	38.48027824
5	-8.91853434	38.48131299
6	-8.91800491	38.48104167

Figure 11. The position and coordinates of the start and ending point of each of the monitoring dives. Points 1 and 2 correspond to the “intertidal” section, 3 and 4 to the “subtidal middle” and 5 and 6 to the “subtidal” section of the meadow.

On a second scope, the sampling division above mentioned also expresses the intensity of other pressures. For instance, in the “intertidal section” the plants are impacted by digging for shell fishing harvesting and by natural factors such as sand deposition due to storms, dissection due to air and temperature variations during higher low tides. In all the sections algae blooms may also affect the plants.

The methodology for monitoring determined by our team was tested in order to be accomplished by the standard sampling method of the meadow – defined as a video line transect - and the logistics and means necessary that are affordable by the project budget. The exploratory sampling dives and planning methodology to determine the monitoring methodology were conducted on the 7th of October, by two marine biologist of Ocean Alive team. For each section a 50m length transect was determined. In this way, the combined length of the 3 line transect covers 150 meters over the 3 pre-determined sections of the meadow. The start and end points of each line transect were chosen with the criteria of covering the maximum number of patches in the corresponding section of the meadow.

The coordinates of the start and end points of each transect line were obtained using QGIS® software (2023) to first mark the desired points on the map with the location of the patches and afterwards extracting from those the longitude and longitude coordinates.

The coordinates were then recorded in as waypoints into a GPS 64S Garmin. Once in the field, the function chart route of the GPS was activated in order to search and find the points, navigating from the boat. In each section, the first and the end points were signaled using surface buoys attached by a rope to weights dropped into the bottom. Starting at the designated point, divers determined the diving direction necessary to reach the end point by using a compass. Along that course, one of the divers (diver 1) deploys the 50-meter line transect on the bottom (Figure 12).

At intervals of 10 meters, the other diver (diver 2) conducts measurements to collect data on the biological indicators - density (ud/m²) and canopy height (cm). The sampling method followed Borum et al., 2004 (European seagrasses: an introduction to monitoring and management).

Seagrass density was measured by counting the number of individual shoots present within a sampling quadrat of 15x15cm located randomly within the patch that was being sampled (Figure 12). Results were afterwards extrapolated to m². Canopy height was sampled by measuring the longest leaf of 5 shoots chosen randomly at each patch.

Figure 12. Picture of a marine biologist from Ocean Alive deploying the measuring tape to create the transect line taking notes of the data collected on the seagrass patch. ©Ocean Alive

When reaching the end point, the first diver checks the corresponding 50 m length of the measuring tape line at the location of the predetermined end point. If confirmed, “diver 1” follows the line transect backwards to the starting point, from that point the diver 1 starts conducting a video line transect along the 50m line. The video is recorded with an Olympus TG Tough, standing at the center of the line and keeping the same depth, as long as conditions allowed so. Once finished the line transect, at the end point, diver 1 starts retrieving the measuring tape back to the starting point. Both divers meet, collect the surface signaling buoys and return to the boat. The process is repeated in order to monitor each section. Biodiversity encountered during the sampling process was also documented through the use of photographs and videos.

The first monitoring dives were conducted on the 8th of October, by the same marine biologists. The logistic operational boat support was provided by the MT “Rotas do Sal”. The here described protocol for systematic monitoring of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow, based on video line transect and biological indicators sampling, will be replicated in the subsequent monitoring activities programed for March 2024, September 2024 and March 2025.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

BASELINE INFORMATION OF THE CAMBALHÃO SEAGRASS MEADOW

1. Mapping and area estimation

The estimate of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow area is 0.35 hectares (3,474.96 m²) (Figure 13). This meadow is composed by several patches that are located within the eastern bay of Cambalhão Island, extending along a rectangle of up to 415 meters in length and up to 340 meters in width (considering a perpendicular direction from the coast) (Figure 14).

Figure 13. Orthomosaic created from the compilation of the 78 photographs taken at 100m of altitude, showing the location and distribution of the seagrass patches, represented as polygons of variable sizes over it. ©Ocean Alive

Point ID	Longitude	Latitude
1	-8.92017589	38.48338932
2	-8.92165919	38.48163645
3	-8.91645820	38.48056133
4	-8.91926066	38.47769102

Figure 14. The position and coordinates of the boundary points that define the extent in which the seagrass patches are comprised.

2. Baseline conditions

2.1. Number, distribution and dimension of the patches of the meadow

The Cambalhão seagrass meadow is composed of 202 seagrass patches, the majority of them are covered permanently by water. Namely, only approximately 64 of the patches are situated in the intertidal section of the meadow (Figure 15), while the remaining 138 are distributed in the subtidal (closer and further away from the island) sections at a maximum depth of ~4m.

The dimensions of the patches that compose the meadow vary from 0.36m² to 233.75m². The mean area of the patches is 17.20m² (± 25.1 SD). The majority of them present an area of between 7.9 m² and 42.3 m².

Figure 15. Picture of a *Zostera noltii* intertidal seagrass patch. ©Ocean Alive

2.2. Species composition of the meadow, biological indicators

The Cambalhão seagrass meadow consists of both monospecific and mixed patches of the seagrass species *Zostera marina* and *Zostera noltii* (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Underwater pictures of the two seagrass species present at the Cambalhão meadow. On the left, *Zostera marina*, and on the right, *Zostera noltii*. ©Ocean Alive

Namely, the species *Z. marina* was observed in 4 out of 5 patches during the baseline transect dives conducted in June and in 26 out of the 52 patches during the exploratory surveys (apneas, shoreline walks). The species *Z. noltii* was (also) observed in 26 out of the 52 patches during the exploratory surveys and just in 1 of the patches found during the baseline transect dives (Table 1).

Table 1. Data on canopy height (cm) and density (ud/m²) expressed in mean values, with the correlated standard deviation (SD) and the number (N) of samples used in the calculus. The data appears differentiated by the three designated zones of the meadow “intertidal”, “subtidal middle” and “subtidal”, as well as by the month in which the sampling took place.

Zone	Species	Canopy height (cm)			Density (ud/m ²)			Month
		Mean	SD	N of samples	Mean	SD	N of samples	
Intertidal	<i>Z.marina</i>	27.80	3.90	5	80.00	NA	1	Oct
Subtidal-midle	<i>Z.marina</i>	31.40	8.35	15	138.67	66.61	3	Oct
Subtidal-midle	<i>Z.marina</i>	32.30	4.70	20	155.56	85.10	4	Jun
Subtidal-midle	<i>Z.noltii</i>	18.60	7.20	10	592.00	203.65	2	Oct
Subtidal-midle	<i>Z.noltii</i>	31.80	3.96	5	133.33	NA	1	Jun
Subtidal	<i>Z.marina</i>	35.27	6.09	15	160.00	89.08	3	Oct

Both species coexist within the meadow area, with a similar presence in the surveyed patches. *Z. marina* predominates in the subtidal part, as suggested by the data and observations made during baseline and monitoring transect dives. The first biological indicators - density and canopy height mean values - of the plants composing the Cambalhão seagrass meadow, were collected in subtidal patches, during June. The estimates here presented are supported by 4 replicates for density

and 20 replicates for canopy height and refer to *Z. marina* only. The average shoot density of *Z. marina* obtained is 151.11 ud/m², with a standard deviation (SD) of \pm 74.37 ud/m², and the average canopy height is 32.2 cm, with a SD of \pm 4.56 cm. Because only one sighting of *Z. noltii* was recorded, we cannot provide estimations of biological indicators for this species (Table 1).

Finally, we would like to mention that seed production by *Z. marina* plants of the Cambalhão meadow was observed in June (Figure 17) suggesting that the meadow is investing in sexual reproduction.

Figure 17. Picture in which the seeds of a plant of *Z. marina* can be spotted within the reproductive structure denominated inflorescence. ©Ocean Alive

2.3 Estimated age of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow,

According with the answers obtained from the questionnaires directed to 8 individuals of the local community, the Cambalhão sand bank has existed in the Sado estuary for at least 45 years, having suffered different modifications in its area and position throughout time. The seagrass meadow adjacent to the island is much more recent, with the participants indicating that the first signs of the existence of a seagrass meadow started in 2018 – 2019 and its establishment has become evident since 2020. Furthermore, all participants have indicated that the seagrass meadow has been expanding with time, with no visible signs of disappearing or loss of area, other than natural seasonal variations. Based on this

source of information, we confirm that Cambalhão seagrass meadow is a recent meadow and estimate that it has less than 5 years of age, by 2023.

2.4 Biodiversity at the Cambalhão seagrass meadow

Several emblematic fauna species live in the Cambalhão seagrass meadow: greater pipefish, eel, cuttlefish, and octopus, are here highlighted (Figure 18A; Figure 18B). These and other species were observed by the team of Ocean Alive during exploratory and monitoring activities and are listed in (Table 2). These include fish species - seabream, mullet, and sand smelt; mollusk species, such as sea slugs and algarve volute, and crustaceans such as spider crabs. Other invertebrates such as sponges and tube worms were also spotted in the area. Furthermore, we observed several algae species, including the brown algae *Dictyota dychotoma* and *Cystoseira* sp)

Table 2. Summary table of the species that were found at the Cambalhão seagrass meadow during the exploratory and monitoring activities. Date of the records was indicated when available.

General classification	Species name	Common name	Date	Source
Anemone	<i>Anemonia viridis</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	Opelet	08/10/2023	PA080702.JPG
Emblematic species of fish	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	European eel	07/10/2023	PA070637.JPG
Mollusk	<i>Aplysia depilans</i> (Gmelin, 1791)	Sea-hare	13/06/2023	P6121998.JPG
Fish	<i>Atherina presbyter</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	Sand smelt		In situ identification
Mollusk	<i>Calliostoma zizyphinum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Painted topshell		In situ identification
Anemone	<i>Cerianthus membranaceus</i> (Spallanzani, 1784)		13/06/2023	P6130055.JPG
Fish	<i>Chelon labrosus</i> (Risso, 1827)	Thick-lipped grey mullet		In situ identification
Red algae	<i>Chondrus crispus</i> (Stackhouse, 1797)	Irish moss		In situ identification
Green algae	<i>Codium</i> sp.		13/06/2023	GOPR4887.JPG
Mollusk	<i>Cymbium olla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Algarve volute		In situ identification
Brown algae	<i>Cystoseira</i> sp.		13/06/2023	GOPR4887.JPG
Brown algae	<i>Dictyota dichotoma</i>		13/06/2023	P6121998.JPG
Fish	<i>Diplodus annularis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		28/07/2023	i-DFb5KwD-X4.jpg
Echinoderm	<i>Echinocardium cordatum</i> (Pennant, 1777)	Sea-potato	08/10/2023	PA080688.JPG
Brown algae	<i>Ectocarpus</i> sp.			In situ identification
Mollusk	Eggs of <i>Aplysia punctata</i> (Cuvier, 1803)	Sea-hare	08/10/2023	PA080687.JPG

Emblematic species of mollusk	Eggs of <i>Sepia officinalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common cuttlefish	08/10/2023	PA080682.JPG
Fish	<i>Gobius</i> sp.			<i>In situ identification</i>
Fish	juvenile <i>Symphodus</i> spp		13/06/2023	P6130044.JPG
Crustacean	<i>Maja squinado</i> (Herbst, 1788)	Spiny spider crab	07/10/2023	PA070649.JPG
Tubeworm	<i>Myxicola infundibulum</i> (Montagu, 1808)		07/10/2023	PA070660.JPG
Emblematic species of mollusk	Octopus vulgaris (Cuvier, 1797)	Common octopus	08/10/2023	PA070660.JPG
Brown algae	<i>Padina pavonica</i> (Thivy, 1960)			<i>In situ identification</i>
Tubeworm	<i>Sabella pavonina</i> Savigny, 1820		08/10/2023	PA080680.JPG
Emblematic species of fish	<i>Syngnathus acus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Greater pipefish	07/10/2023	PA070624.JPG
Seagrass	<i>Zostera marina</i> (Linnaeus, 1753)	Eel-grass		<i>In situ identification</i>
Seagrass seeds	<i>Zostera marina</i> (Linnaeus, 1753) seeds		13/06/2023	P6130008.JPG
Seagrass	<i>Zostera noltei</i> (Hornemann, 1832)	Dwarf eel-grass		<i>In situ identification</i>

Figure 18 A. Picture of a European eel found at the Cambalhão seagrass meadow. ©Ocean Alive

Figure 18 B. Picture of a common octopus (on the left) and of a greater pipefish (on the right) found at the Cambalhão seagrass meadow. ©Ocean Alive

3. Threats and pressures

3.1. Natural

The main natural pressures we have identified are southern storms and algal blooms. As an example, in 2023, there was a significant storm in March. The waves

destroyed part of the dune in an area close to the center of Cambalhão island. That led to deposition of sediment on a part of the intertidal meadow.

Based on dive observations and case studies throughout this period, the meadow was found to have algal blooms in March 2023, June 2023 and October 2023 (Figure 19), while in January 2023, July 2023 and August 2023, we did not observe any algae bloom associated with the meadow. Algal blooms are periods in which the abundance of one or more species of algae significantly increases. This is typically associated with a higher availability of nitrogen compounds in the water, which stimulate the growth of algae. The occurrence and frequency of these events are influenced by various factors, including water temperature, abiotic interactions, and pollutants discharged from rivers or urban run-off (Sarkar, 2018). Seagrasses, as well as algae, require nitrogen for their metabolic processes and growth. Consequently, an excessive proliferation of algae can lead to competition not only for light availability but also for nutrients. This competition can potentially have adverse effects on seagrasses if the algae grow exponentially and eventually cover the seagrass meadow, inhibiting photosynthesis in seagrasses (Bittick et al., 2018). However, some studies have demonstrated that certain algal species can promote nitrogen uptake and successfully coexist with the seagrasses, thereby preventing opportunistic macroalgae blooms in nitrogen-poor environments (Alexandre et al., 2017).

Figure 19. Picture of a seagrass patch covered by algae during an algal bloom. ©Ocean Alive

From the answers obtained from the questionnaires, this information has been corroborated by the local community, with the winter storms being identified as a major source for area variation in the Cambalhão sand bank. Furthermore, the occurrence of turf algae that grow over the seagrass and compete for essential nutrients and sunlight is also seen as a problem affecting the meadow. These algae are commonly found accumulating in the southernmost portion of the sandbank (which is oriented towards the ocean) and end up being transported into the area of the seagrass meadow, especially during spring tides. According to the locals, these turf algae are mostly present in the area of the seagrass meadow during summer months, but they have been starting to appear sooner in the year (from April onwards) and in increasing amounts.

Additionally, the targeted members of the local community have identified the variations seen in the area of the Cambalhão sand bank as an additional impact factor for the seagrass meadow. Even though the island has suffered many changes in its area throughout the years, only recently has it started to stabilize its position and displaying a stabilized growth in area. A cause for this is attributed to the deposits of dredging done in Sado Estuary, which are placed further offshore but ended up being transported back into the entrance of the Estuary and accumulate in the area of the sand bank. Additionally, the natural currents of the estuary also promote sand transportation from the surrounding beaches, which also contributes to the growth of the sand bank.

3.2. Anthropogenic

From the answers obtained in the questionnaire to the local community, different fishing practices have been identified as causes for degradation in the seagrass meadow. The most impactful one is grid dredging, which has been practiced by hand or by boat. Grid dredging is mostly targeted at bivalve fishing (namely for clams – *Ruditapes decussatus* – and cockles – *Cerosterna edule*) and involves dragging a cage through the seafloor to look for buried bivalves, which when done on seagrass areas can be a major cause for plant destruction (Erftemeijer et al., 2006).

Other fishing practices occurring in the seagrass meadow area of Cambalhão that have been identified are different forms of netting, pot fishing, underwater fishing and fishing using hand rake and hand hoe (Figure 20). These fishing practices have been identified with both recreational and professional purposes. The extent of impact of these fishing practices was not known by Ocean Alive's team before the start of the project.

Figure 20. Pictures showing examples of the destructive techniques used for shellfish gathering at the intertidal part of the Cambalhão meadow (Above and below right images), and of the shellfish that is normally collected in that area (below left image). ©Ocean Alive

On a morning during a low spring tide of an august weekend, it has been identified by Ocean Alive's team the occurrence of 35 people fishing for bivalves on most southeastern edge of the meadow (Figure 21). Intensive clam harvesting has the potential to lead to a significant reduction in the previously accumulated superficial organic carbon within the sediment of seagrass meadows, as demonstrated by research carried out on the Ria Formosa *Zostera noltii* meadow (Román et al., 2022). Other important impacts on the seagrass meadow caused by anthropogenic activity are improper waste disposal and unregulated and unconscious boating practices, specially verified on the way that anchors are deployed on the seagrass meadow area.

Figure 21. Shellfish harvesters at the intertidal section of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow (on the left), and scars left by those activities on the cover of a *Z. noltii* intertidal patch (on the right) ©Ocean Alive

EDUCATION AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

3. Ambassadors among the maritime touristic (MT) enterprises- “Seagrass Guardians”.

We educated and trained 19 maritime tourism staff members of 8 enterprises. The companies that were selected work mainly in boat transfers to and from Cambalhão sand bank, boat tours around the Sado estuary and private onboard events that include the sand bank as part of the experience. These results were obtained from the educational activity held in March and the individual approaches held during July and August.

The questionnaires done to MT operators after the month of August included 4 participants from different companies. It was mentioned by all participants that they did not adapt much of their working routines after talking with Ocean Alive’s team. For the most part, the location of the Cambalhão sandbank that they frequent, either for deploying tourists or during boat tours, is on the south-eastern edge of the sandbank, a deeper and safer region for boat traffic, which is far away from the seagrass meadow. The area including the seagrass meadow is shallower so it is not frequented by MT operators as it may hinder their professional activity. Therefore, they did not feel the need to adapt their boat routes.

Additionally, only the operators that perform boat tours and private onboard events mentioned that they attempted to raise awareness among tourists about the importance of seagrass and the Cambalhão meadow. The operators that perform boat transfers mentioned that the time they have between boat rides is limited and they do not have much time to talk with their clients between services.

However, it was mentioned by all operators that the information provided by Ocean Alive’s team was very useful and added to the knowledge they previously

had on seagrass. Especially regarding the different ecosystem services and the location of the seagrass meadows in the Sado Estuary. All operators demonstrated openness to keep cooperating with Ocean Alive and are interested in receiving additional supporting data that they can share on their public platforms and social media, such as underwater and drone footage, maps and relevant information on the importance of seagrass.

Additionally, suggestions have been made to increase their range of action to raise awareness, such as the creation of an onboard manual with illustrative pictures that could easily be consulted by operators and tourists on the importance of seagrass, the creation of stickers to identify them as Seagrass Guardians and the development together with local authorities of a legal safe-conduct guide to be followed in seagrass areas (Figure 22)

Figure 22. Rotas do Sal MT operator, displaying the poster and leaflets given by Ocean Alive to be displayed on their facilities.. ©Ocean Alive

It was also notable that out of the 8 maritime tourism companies that were approached, the ones that had a physical store in the Setúbal region (all present in Table 3 with the exception of Taxiboat) displayed the poster provided by Ocean Alive’s team on their facilities and made Ocean Alive’s leaflet available for their customers.

Table 3. Summary of the maritime tourism companies that were targeted by Ocean Alive’s team for education, awareness and cooperation during the summer months. Includes the main activities developed by each company, the number of trained operators and the date at which they were approached.

Maritime tourism company	Main activity	Number of operators	Awareness date
Boat Center	Boat rentals	1	15/03/2023
Vertigem Azul	Dolphin watching, boat tours, private onboard events	3	15/03/2023
Rotas do Sal	Dolphin watching, boat tours, private onboard events	3	15/03/2023
Sado Emotions	Dolphin watching, boat tours, private onboard events	4	05/07/2023
Boat Ride Sado	Boat transfers	1	06/07/2023
Nallha	Boat transfers	5	27/07/2023
Natural Park	Boat transfers	1	27/07/2023
Taxiboat	Boat transfers	1	04/08/2023

4. Awareness towards sustainable anchoring practices.

Before this study, we had an estimate provided by different MT operators that on a weekend day in August, the number of boats visiting the Cambalhão sandbank varied between 80 and 150, averaging at around 100 boats per weekend day in August. The same operators have indicated that these numbers are substantially lower in the months of July and September.

For the 2023 season, Ocean Alive’s awareness campaign at Cambalhão sandbank occurred during the first three weekends of August, which was described as the season with highest influence of tourists. It was not possible to carry awareness efforts in the last weekend of August as the weather conditions were not appropriate. No further efforts were conducted during July and September as the number of tourists heading to Cambalhão sandbank had in fact dropped substantially. This was possible due to cooperation with the local maritime tourism operators Nallha, Natural Park and Taxi boat, which offered to transport Ocean Alive’s teams to and from Cambalhão sandbank.

During the month of August, Ocean Alive’s team counted by the end of a weekend day a minimum of 58 and maximum of 128 boats (Figure 23). In total, Ocean Alive’s team reached 543 people who were spending their day at the Cambalhão sandbank, which represented 185 boats.

Out of the people that participated in the questionnaire presented by the end of each interaction, 42% were not aware of what seagrass meadows were and thus

became informed. Around 20% of the participants represented repeated interactions which display a certain degree of regularity on the people that attend the Cambalhão sandbank during summer for spending the day.

Figure 23. Picture taken in August of 2023, at the Cambalhão Island, where we could observe numerous recreational boat anchoring within the seagrass meadow. ©Ocean Alive

Additionally, Ocean Alive's awareness teams were present in 9 other locations in the Sado estuary, reaching 1594 people, representing 406 boats. Around 18% of participants represented repeated interactions.

Lastly, leaflets and posters were distributed in 14 different local businesses, where it was included 3 different marinas, 8 MTs, 1 fishing shop, 1 restaurant and 1 recreational navigation school. Per site, 5 to 7 leaflets and 1 poster were distributed.

MONITORING

1. Video line transects - october 2023

The outcomes derived from the density and canopy height measurements carried out on October 8th provide a comprehensive perspective on these parameters across the spectrum of pressures to which the plants in the patches are subjected, namely, low, medium, high that correspond to the zone in which they are located (respectively; subtidal, subtidal middle, intertidal).

Plant density is higher the further away from the island the patch is located and the lesser the pressures. In order to support this preliminary X-Ray of the meadow, here we present the data on biological indicators collected. Videos conducted along the transects can be accessed here using the provided email account ([Video transect](#)).

In the “intertidal section”, *Z. marina* exhibited an average canopy height of 27.80 cm (with a standard deviation, SD of 3.90 cm) and a density of 80.00 individuals per square meter (ud/m²). Transitioning to the “subtidal middle section” *Z. marina* displayed a mean canopy height of 31.40 cm (SD: 8.35 cm) and a density of 138.67 ud/m² (SD: 66.61 ud/m²).

This zone also hosted *Z. noltii*, which exhibited a canopy mean of 18.60 cm (SD: 7.29 cm) and a mean density of 592.00 ud/m² (SD: 203.65 ud/m²). Moving further away from the coast, within the “subtidal section”, only *Z. marina* was identified. Here, it displayed mean canopy height values of 35.27 cm (SD: 6.09 cm) and a density of 160.00 ud/m² (SD: 89.08 ud/m²) (Table 1; Figure 24).

Figure 24. Graphical representation of the canopy height and density with their respective units of measure, along the seasons for both species *Zostera marina* and *Zostera noltii*.

NEXT STEPS

To increase the information about the value of the Cambalhão meadow?

1. Include biodiversity assessment on monitoring line transect procedures.
2. Monitor reproductive investment of the meadow.

3. Monitor the dynamic of number patches and area of the meadow.
4. Investigate the effect of the algae blooms on the development of the meadow.
5. Insist on partnership for investigating the genetic identity of the plants composing the meadow.
6. Measure the benefits of ecosystem services of the meadow such as carbon and nitrogen sequestration

To increase the awareness about the importance of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow - summer vacationers and users

8. Collect the opinion of the Cambalhão island summer users - vacationers, shellfish gatherers, underwater hunters and MTs - to find out how we can improve the protection of the meadow
9. Complement the direct awareness of the users with marine education actions at the meadow during low tides on summer weekend august days
10. Consult local governmental and nature protection entities about the possibility of implementing a removable information panel about the meadow on the sandy island.
11. Engage MTs in spreading the word by (1) producing social media information materials that these enterprises can share (2) producing an onboard manual with illustrative pictures and information about the meadow that could easily be consulted by operators and tourists.

To increase the implementation of good navigational and anchoring practices in the meadow.

12. Collect the opinion of the Cambalhão boat users - to find out how we can improve the protection the information and signaling about good practices.
13. Maintain the good navigational and anchoring practices awareness campaign targeting Cambalhão island summer boat vacationers.
14. Mitigate the effect of very low tides in involuntary anchoring in the meadows. Previous assessment of the risk of this pressure can be made based on analysis of the number of days with high tides in the month. If we take August 2023 as an example, there are 6 days (tides up to 0.7).

To increase the role of MTs as Guardians of the Cambalhão seagrass meadow

14. Consolidate the idea of the creation of stickers to identify MTs as Seagrass Guardians.
15. Development with the Mts and local authorities a legal safe-conduct guide to be followed in seagrass areas.
16. Provide further training opportunities.

To avoid the degradation of the intertidal patches by summer shellfish gatherers

17. Raising awareness about why not shell fishing at the seagrass meadows through one to one conversations and dialogues. This will be Ocean Alive's theme of action from 2024 onwards and will therefore be addressed across the board in the following projects.

To deter bottom trawling from the Cambalhão bay

18. Engage “BivalMar”, the local cooperative of shellfish harvesters and professional boat bottom trawling, to assess the pressure of professional shellfish farming on the Cambalhão seagrass meadow area towards the status of a voluntary no-take zone.

MEDIA SUPPORT

Photographs and video recordings of baseline, monitoring and awareness activities, biodiversity found at the meadow can be reach by the provided email account for this purpose at [Fotos & Vídeos](#).

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Annex I

S. R.
MINISTÉRIO DA DEFESA NACIONAL
AUTORIDADE AERONÁUTICA NACIONAL
Gabinete da Autoridade Aeronáutica Nacional
HISTÓRICO / HISTORY N.º AAN 51682/2023

Data	Estado	Utilizador
2023-08-09 23:32:55	Submetida	João Luís Esteves

Boa noite ,

Serve o presente recibo para confirmar a receção na Autoridade Aeronáutica Nacional do requerimento para Levantamentos Aéreos formulado por João Luís Ramos Jorge Esteves 12992436, que ficou registado com o número 51682/2023

A Autoridade Aeronáutica Nacional
General João Guilherme Rosado Cartaxo Alves

Assinatura

Annex II

Annex II: Questionnaire on Cambalhão sandbank and its Seagrass meadow

- a. Description of the informer
 1. For how many years have you been going to Cambalhão sandbank?
 2. In what time of the year do you most visit the Cambalhão sandbank?
 3. How often do you go to Cambalhão sandbank?
 4. What kind of activities do you do at Cambalhão sandbank?

- b. Status of the seagrass meadow
 1. Have you noticed the presence of a seagrass meadow near the Cambalhão sandbank? If your answer is yes, for how long do you know about its existence, can you identify a year?
 2. How has the seagrass meadow developed with time? Has it grown / shrank? Have you noticed if the seagrass patches have increased /decreased?
 - 2.1. Can you identify a time where the seagrass meadow has completely disappeared?
 3. In your opinion, which external factors (natural and/or anthropogenic) are affecting the Cambalhão sandbank and its seagrass meadow the most?
 - 3.1. We have noticed that the seagrass meadow is often affected by blooms of turf algae. Do you have any information on this? Is there a time of the year where the amount of algae in the seagrass meadow is higher?

- c. For maritime tourism operators only
After receiving information on the importance of seagrass meadows and the Cambalhão sandbank by Ocean Alive's team:
 1. Did you change the location where you deploy your clients? Are you aware if you are doing this out of the seagrass meadow area?
 2. Did you help raising awareness towards the importance of seagrass meadows? Did you use any of the materials (leaflets and posters) provided by Ocean Alive to do this, either for your clients or staff?
 3. Has your knowledge on seagrass meadows improved with the information shared by Ocean Alive? If yes, in what way?
 4. Did you miss any information or important detail that was not made clear by Ocean Alive?
 5. Are you interested in receiving additional supporting materials (such as more information, photos, videos and maps) about seagrass meadows and Cambalhão sandbank to be used in your activity?
 6. To you have any suggestions that may help us improve the protection of seagrass meadows in the Sado estuary?